

Increasing Awareness of Researcher Mental Health

Proposed by Brian Cahill

URL: <https://escmp.euroscience.org/proposal/view/997>

Status: Draft

Programme: Careers Programme

Format: Workshop

Duration: 1h15

Theme: Added value and characteristics of evolving research-based careers

Abstract: The European Research Area currently faces a massive challenge in the form of the psychological distress of researchers at all levels of research. The number of reported cases of stress, isolation, burn-out, depression and other mental disorders are exponentially growing. These symptoms may be exacerbated by increasingly high levels of researcher mobility due to the lower degree of emotional maintenance. Very little has been done to address this issue at local, national and European levels. Currently small, often localized attempts have been taken to aid researchers in distress. The UK-based Vitae network, the work of Trinity College Dublin and small bottom-up European researcher initiatives, such as, the Rumo Platform or TranSkills, are relevant examples of ways to address this challenge. On a global level, the WHO has been advocating for the promotion of good practices within organisations which universities should adopt. In 2016, the Bratislava Declaration of Young Researchers proposed that implementing sustainable career trajectories and flexible research environments would support a healthy work-life balance and reduce stress for Europe's researchers. Most importantly, the implementation of family-friendly policies that encourage a positive work-life balance can improve female participation in research. The organisers of this workshop want to stress the timeliness of this issue, as this psychological epidemic will have a significant effect on the output of European research, risking the European Commission's objective of putting Europe into a leading position in global research publications. This workshop is being organised with the involvement of major opinion leaders, researchers, service providers, and researcher community representatives affected by and working on the phenomenon of the high levels of mental stress experienced by researchers.

Target audience: Scientists, Media, Policy makers, General public, Students

Cross-cutting approaches: Gender issues

Relevance of the selected approaches: In this session, the audience will be invited to reflect on three topics [means for financial support; policy development; knowledge sharing] related to the development of a healthy work-life balance in academia and how this can lead to positive developments for researcher mental health. Participants will be split into groups and work towards developing recommendations for solutions. The activity that the session organisers will propose uses non-formal means in order to promote dynamism between the audience and speakers who will be engaged with the audience/participants while they carry out the tasks. In the end, the speakers will comment on the proposed solutions and a final debate will be promoted to finish the session with a general reflection. Results from the session will be used afterwards to produce research and suggest guidelines for policies within the topic of how a healthy work-life balance can improve mental health in academia.

The structure of the workshop is the following:

We start with our invited speakers and we give a brief overview on the topic, from a number of angles. Afterwards we split the audience in groups to discuss the most stressing issues, presented by the experts. The groups will need to pick at least 1 issue and discuss recommendations in terms of

- suggest means of financial (internal, external) support
- suggest a policy/legislation
- suggest knowledge sharing/knowledge generation activities

We hand out post-it papers to groups to record their recommendations, and present them briefly to the audience. We also put them on a board we previously install in the room. At the end all people will get to vote on the suggestions and promote the best policy ideas. The chair will summarise the output, and the panel of experts will provide feedback for the best ideas.

During the session notes will be taken and all the ideas will be recorded and used for a policy paper addressing researchers' mental health awareness.

Special requirements and demands: Room suitable for workshop.
Post-it Notes.
Markers.

Does the session organiser (or a speaker of the session) envisage to propose an event in the Science in the City festival (same dates as ESOF) about the same topic oriented towards the public (this should be in French or in English and French) ?:
No

Does the session organiser (or speakers of the session) envisage to participate in an event in the Science in the City festival on a topic related to that of the session (this should be in French or in English and French) ? : No

Status	Name	Email	Gndr	Position	Organisation	Country	Role	Reason for inviting
Submitter	Brian Cahill		M	Chair of MCAA / Research Group Leader	Marie Curie Alumni Association / Institut für Bioprozess und Analysentechnik	GERMANY	Submitter	

Status	Name	Email	Gndr	Position	Organisation	Country	Role	Reason for inviting
Confirmed	Brian Cahill		M	Chair of MCAA / Research Group Leader	MCAA - Marie Curie Alumni Association	GERMANY	Moderator	Brian Cahill is Chair of the Marie Curie Alumni Association, an association representing over 10,000 mobile researchers. In this role, he provides advice to a wide range of researchers, who may experience issues related to stress and mental health, for example, early-stage researchers, who have left their home country for the first time, or postdoctoral researchers juggling a career in research with the demands of raising a young family.
Confirmed	Mark Robinson		M	Student Counsellor	Student Counselling Service, Trinity College Dublin	IRELAND	Panellist	Mark Robinson is a very experienced practitioner in aiding researchers to cope with mental problems, which viewpoint is essential for the proposed workshop. He practices as an integrative therapist drawing on humanistic, emotion-focused, psychodynamic and cognitive behavioural frameworks. He also co-ordinates all training requests into the service and takes part in research in the area of emotion-focused therapy.

Status	Name	Email	Gndr	Position	Organisation	Country	Role	Reason for inviting
Confirmed	Francisco Gonçalves		M	Marie Curie Early Stage Researcher / Psychologist	University of Leicester / rumo platform	UNITED KINGDOM	Panellist	Francisco Valente Gonçalves works on topics such as motivation, stress management and decision-making processes. Francisco provides psychological counselling within an integrative and humanistic client-based perspective to different types of populations since 2011. He works in different contexts: hospitals, prisons, universities and private practice. In 2016 Francisco co-founded rumo online platform that provides psychological counselling to expats in 6 countries and in 4 languages.
Confirmed	Gábor Kismihók		M	Senior Researcher	University of Amsterdam	NETHERLANDS	Panellist	Dr. Gábor Kismihók has been engaged in establishing a comprehensive transversal skills training for researchers both in industry and academia in Europe for the past four years. Providing concrete training in mental health awareness to both researchers and their supervisors was one of the cornerstones of this activity. Currently he is launching the TranSkills initiative, which aims at scaling the above-mentioned activities up to a European level together with the Marie Curie Alumni Association.

Status	Name	Email	Gndr	Position	Organisation	Country	Role	Reason for inviting
Confirmed	Susan Guthrie		F	Research Leader	RAND Europe	UNITED KINGDOM	Panellist	Susan Guthrie's primary research interests are in the area of science and innovation policy. Of her recent and ongoing work of most relevance for this session is her work on the international mobility of researchers and, in particular, her recent review of the evidence around the mental health needs of researchers. She found that levels of burnout appear higher among university staff than in general working populations and are comparable to 'high-risk' groups such as healthcare workers.
Contacted	Katia Levecque		F	Assistant Professor	University of Ghent	BELGIUM	Panellist	Katia Levecque's main interests are occupational health and well-being, work organization and employment conditions, industrial relations, labor markets and welfare states. Most recent work includes the study on the work organization and mental health problems of young researchers in Flemish universities, benchmarking the prevalence of the problems to that of other highly educated groups. The study was published in Research Policy in March 2017 and has triggered a lot of attention worldwide.

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Contacted	Sara Cameron		F	PhD Candidate	University of Strathclyde	UNITED KINGDOM	Panellist	Sara Cameron is a PhD Candidate and a member of MCAA. She was a PhD student in Germany until she left to return home to Scotland, where she is now doing PhD on a very similar topic. She can report on the challenges facing young mobile researchers undergoing international mobility.

Supporting documents

- 1 CV Gabor Kismihok
- 2 CV Mark Robinson
- 3 CV Susan Guthrie
- 4 CV Francisco Goncalves
- 5 CV Brian Cahill